

Application of SHEWHART Control Chart Method in a Satellite Production Study

Rahmi CENAN¹

¹ St. Clements University, PhD Student in Business Administration, Orcid ID: 0000-0002-1400-9255, Mail: rcenan@outlook.com

1

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ABSTRACT

The fast growth of technology and growing rates have resulted in a highly competitive atmosphere between the conditions. Companies are raising output to stay up with the competition and respond to the disruption. Companies in this circumstance were continuously ensuring the quality of their products and services. The breadth of these quality control applications is expanding, which increases interest in quality solutions. Quality boosts competitiveness, allowing them to grow their market reach, and attracts new clients. It is also critical for individuals to utilize their assets strategically in order to attain long-term success. The focus of both producers and markets toward quality goods has contributed significantly to the foundation of our concept of quality.

Satellites, which are tiny objects that move on a route around a much bigger object, include several subsystems that replace different capabilities and strengths throughout their intended

CURRENT SCIENCE

mission programs. One of these core subsystems is the propulsion subsystem, which guarantees that space equipment operates safely and reliably during the satellite's lifetime in orbit. The satellite subsystem regulates the movement of the satellite during its installation and guarantees that it stays in place.

Satellites that have been finished go through a variety of rigorous testing procedures to verify they can perform perfectly in space settings. One of these checks is the alignment check. Because it is impossible to physically intervene from the ground in the event of a malfunction after the satellite has been launched, it is critical that alignment measurements of all equipment in the satellite production stages be performed carefully and quickly, that failure analyses be performed, and that negative results be evaluated.

This work used variable quantity SHEWHART control charts to assess the accuracy of alignment measurements taken throughout the design phase. This control chart analysis approach utilized in satellite operations will also help with transition operation applications and theoretical investigations.

Keywords: *Satellite, Quality, Shewhart Control Charts, Alignment, Thrust Systems,*

INTRODUCTION

Satellites are known to be subjected to extreme space environments throughout the design phase, and the manufacturing process is prepared appropriately. The incorporation of high-quality goods into everyday company operations has started to gain traction in the satellite operation industry, as well as in other manufacturing sectors. Because of the use of quality control graphics, the product that appeared in satellite manufacturing components was enlarged throughout the process. This strategy has made it simpler for persons who have gained satellite manufacturing and testing processes to read more clearly and accurately. According to Ertuğrul and Özçil (2015), quality is a notion that people examine and interpret differently while making economic and social decisions.

CURRENT SCIENCE

With technological advancements, Statistical Quality Control has evolved into a dynamic framework that satisfies consumer distributions, maintains industry competitiveness, monitors the process, identifies potential flaws, and allows for the implementation of quality techniques. Statistical Quality Control refers to the techniques used to identify the right quality level and change the system by studying factors throughout production. Furthermore, this control covers the distribution of a wide range of issues. Theories do not explain the changes and complicated sequence of certain changes that must be solved or controlled. In many domains, Statistical Quality Control is included in quality improvement programs as well as other statistical and growth strategies (Allen 2006).

AIM

The goal of this procedure is to offer control charts from quality tools used throughout satellite manufacturing, assembly, integration, and testing phases, as well as for the quality presentation of goods or products. The artificial satellite production enterprise attempted to minimize the unpredictability of the post-production test process by collecting angular data from subsystem alignment measurement tests.

The propulsion system alignment testing method, together with the use of common quality control tools like control charts, may decrease production variability and monitor process control.

SCIENTIFIC BASIS OF THE STUDY

Statistical Quality Control Charts

Process control methods are often employed in the business to increase and monitor product ranges. Various control charts are offered to monitor process variables and detect unusual events that adversely impact quality (Noorossana & Vaghefi, 2006). Businesses like several

CURRENT SCIENCE

different sorts of control charts. One of them is the Shewhart Control Chart. Devices may function normally in space satellites, as they do in any other electronic environment. The life and performance of equipment may be directly correlated with operational circumstances. As a result, electronic components must function within the design parameters specified. Because each device has its unique working environment, temperature, and performance range, it is done in accordance with these conditions.

The application was carried out utilizing the Shewhart control chart, which is one of the most acceptable metrics for monitoring the average production process in recent years. As a consequence of the mistakes discovered during the satellite propulsion subsystem test, control charts for thruster dimensions were reviewed.

The Shewhart chart approach is intended to provide more effective and exact findings, and a research has been presented to lower test costs while also benefiting the company. This condition allows for the technical interpretation of various factors relevant to improved observation, tracking, and management of process event information. The Shewhart control chart, which spans across a larger region with a normal distribution, has emerged as the most successful way for rapidly detecting mistakes and flaws throughout the testing process.

Shewhart $\bar{X}$ and R (Range) Control Chart Methodology

It is critical to monitor process modifications by collecting adequate quantities at regular intervals after the production or testing phases of the company. This strategy allows for the identification of the causes of business changes and the implementation of essential modifications. Furthermore, the sample values collected following the test step must be quantifiable.

Shewhart quality charts are regarded as one of the most essential ways of quality control, establishing the reasons of production failures, and implementing incentive measures. In these parts, it is highly beneficial to utilize the process performance and determine the sources of variance in industrial goods (Topalidou & Psarakis, 2009).

CURRENT SCIENCE

A Shewhart chart is a graph of observations over time, with upper and lower control limits placed at intervals between stands and below the central line (Vries & Conlin, 2005). This approach uses subgroup measurements to derive $\bar{X}$ means and R range values. $\bar{X}$ is the average of these programs' findings, and $\bar{R}$ is the quantity of their average values. The $\bar{X}$ update reflects the arithmetic mean of the variables in the mean group and tests for a change in the process mean. The R range ranges vary in the big and small values found between the ratios, allowing you to observe changes in standard deviations during the process. To develop these systems, many techniques are used as subgroups. The application requires a subgroup size of $n < 8$ and a minimum of m subgroup values.

The formulas used in the study are as follows (Şahin, 2019):

$$\bar{X} = \frac{X_{11} + X_{12} + X_{13} + X_{14} + \dots + X_{1n}}{n} \tag{1}$$

$$R_1 = \text{Max}(X_{11} + X_{12} + X_{13} + X_{14} + \dots + X_{1n}) - \text{Min}(X_{11} + X_{12} + X_{13} + X_{14} + \dots + X_{1n}) \tag{2}$$

$$\bar{\bar{X}} = \frac{\bar{X}_1 + \bar{X}_2 + \bar{X}_3 + \bar{X}_4 + \dots + \bar{X}_m}{m} \tag{3}$$

CURRENT SCIENCE

The measurement values contained herein”, $\bar{X}$ The average control limits of the graph are calculated with the following formulas:

$$\bar{R} = \frac{R_1 + R_2 + R_3 + R_4 + \dots R_m}{m} \quad (4)$$

$$AKS = \bar{\bar{X}} - A_2 * \bar{R} \quad (5)$$

$$OÇ = \bar{\bar{X}} \quad (6)$$

$$UKS = \bar{\bar{X}} + A_2 * \bar{R} \quad (7)$$

R range speed control limits are calculated using the formulas given below:

$$AKS = D_3 * \bar{R} \quad (8)$$

$$OÇ = \bar{R} \quad (9)$$

$$UKS = D_4 * \bar{R} \quad (10)$$

CURRENT SCIENCE

A_2 , D_3 and D_4 in these equations are read from the coefficient table in Table 1 below.

A_2 was taken as = 0.577 .

$D_3 = 0.00$ and $D_4 = 2.114$ were taken.

Table 1: Control Limits Factor Table

n	A_2	D_3	D_4	d_2
2	1.880	0.000	3.267	1.128
3	1.023	0.000	2.574	1.693
4	0.729	0.000	2.282	2.059
5	0.577	0.000	2.114	2.326
6	0.483	0.000	2.004	2.534

As a result of these programs, it is necessary to determine the existence of the points of the control limit values.

The control chart resulting from all the studies found should generally look similar to the table in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Control Diagram

The graph shows three vendors, the center line (C) and the upper and lower control limits (UKS and AKS). The center line shows the point at which the relevant process characteristic should be true if there is no unusual variability in the process.

APPLICATION OF SHEWART METHOD

In this section; A satellite production and operation unit, the production process is kept under control in the test phase after production. Satellite Propulsion Subsystem Alignment Measurement test example. Measurements were made in degrees on all three axes, x angle, y angle and z angle. Here, the volume was added from five measurement dimensions. In this context, since the transition volume is greater than 1 and less than 8, this, average and R range control diagram were used. $\bar{X}$ The subsystem alignment measurement test setup of an artificial satellite is given in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2: Thrust Subsystem Alignment Measurement Test Setup (ESA, 2015)

Application Method

In fact, the Shewhart control chart approach was used to evaluate the technical data gathered from samples collected by the test team at regular intervals as part of the thrust subsystem alignment stage test. Necessary recommendations were provided to the satellite operator in order to improve the dependability of the test measurements and overall quality. In the application phase of the study, the data collected to produce a quality control chart was arranged using the Excel application software. The data $\bar{X}$ and R control charts were transformed to Shewhart control charts using the procedures. Previous experiences are utilized extensively throughout the satellite manufacturing process and during test activity intervals.

Application Subject

In general, all satellites put into space for communication, military, meteorological, and other data updates travel in elliptical or circular orbits around the earth's equator based on their locations and distances. All artificial satellites constructed are subjected to several activity tests, such as subsystem alignment measurement tests, at various points throughout their service life after being launched into space.

Satellite manufacture and testing are inherently complicated, necessitating precise maintenance methods. As a result, the angular values obtained during the Alignment Measurement tests are assessed in the orbital environment to guarantee that all propulsion machines, which are individually evaluated for satellites and components, function properly.

The purpose of the application is to determine if the angular values acquired as a consequence of the measurements belonging to the combined groups stay within the required range after the alignment measurement test of an artificial satellite. The angular data generated from the alignment results test is stored in each measurement result record for quality control purposes. All-important data collected from reviewing the measurement are immediately received from the current quality control section. The angular values obtained from the test results are used as the foundation.

APPLICATION

The satellite subsystem is the system responsible for activities such as orientation changes, detail control, and satellite distortion in the recorded installation, enabling the satellite to stay or move inside the installation. Alignment is the practice of combining with reference axes to guarantee that the design process is documented.

The subsystem protects the satellite by assuring precise movement in its position, whilst the alignment images and proper holding and fixing of the thrusters contribute to satellite protection by insuring the moving shot. A satellite, for example, has excellent location, communication,

CURRENT SCIENCE

and fuel consumption capabilities when firing at the proper angle during its guiding maneuver. In reality, due to the vacuum air temperature of 4 K (-269.15 o C) in space, the operational test team performs some flexibility tests, such as the propulsion subsystem, to ensure that the satellite is in control of its performance requirements after production and to speed up the design process. Alignment measurement tests are performed both before and after the tests to ensure the right viewpoint.

Satellite alignment examinations often include the use of pointing instruments such as theodolites or dividing mirrors. Pointing devices, which are critical in terms of satellite positioning, are installed on certain components such as antennas, solar sensors, and thrusters on artificial satellites to utilize their mission performance during the manufacturing and testing phases. These alignment test measurements taken with pointing devices offer effective control services by extending the mission life of satellites.

Alignment work is performed on communication, research, and observation spacecraft, as well as all other space vehicles, using sensitive measurement instruments in the locations specified in the design area. The propulsion system comprises of a primary thrust engine and many auxiliary thrust engines. All of these installations must be properly aligned and securely fastened.

Precision alignment measurements guarantee that the satellite will continue to operate successfully throughout its lifetime. Misalignment of the main and auxiliary thrusters results in increased fuel consumption, reducing the satellite's mission length and raising its cost. Alignment measurements identify and fix mistakes produced by the marking device and sensor sensitivity, assembly, integration faults, and violence effects, as well as tiny negativities. Furthermore, data gathered throughout the design process are updated after satellite measurement and alignment testing. The maximum error levels permitted for the satellites' performance movements and characteristics are calculated, as well as the suitable error range, which is assured to be within the limit.

From the perspective of thrust subsystem alignment, the satellite is divided into five regions: the first region is the east panel, the second region is the west panel, the third region is the north

CURRENT SCIENCE

panel, the fourth region is the south panel, and the fifth region is the bottom panel. The surface position angle measurement data on the panel where the thrusters are positioned in each location are divided into lower and higher measurement limits:

1. Region $+89^{\circ}$ to $+89.02^{\circ}$,

Region 2 is between $+89.1^{\circ}$ and $+89.12^{\circ}$,

3. Region $+89.2^{\circ}$ to $+89.25^{\circ}$,

4. Region $+89.3^{\circ}$ to $+89.36^{\circ}$,

5. Region $+90^{\circ}$ to $+90.01^{\circ}$,

The alignment has been corrected to meet the measurement limitations, and the condition of the propulsion equipment in this location will be evaluated.

Table 2 shows the 20 unique angular values for each region's look.

Table 2: 20 Measurement Data Sets

CURRENT SCIENCE

Sample N	1. Region	2. Region	3. Region	4. Region	5. Region	X Average	R Range
1	85,0	87,1	93,8	95	96,2	91,4	11,2
2	85,6	87,5	94,9	90	96,9	91,0	11,3
3	85,9	88,3	89,1	90,1	94,8	89,6	8,9
4	86,2	89,5	95	96,9	95,7	92,7	10,7
5	75,0	92	90,8	96,1	94,6	89,7	21,1
6	85,9	91,9	89,7	94,1	98,7	92,1	12,8
7	89,0	91,1	93,7	93,2	98,1	93,0	9,1
8	88,5	89,9	92,8	95,9	97,5	92,9	9,0
9	87,4	88,8	94,1	97	94	92,3	9,6
10	85,2	87,9	91,8	91,3	112	93,6	26,8
11	86,6	90,8	91,3	92,8	97,9	91,9	11,3
12	87,1	91,3	89	96,7	98,3	92,5	11,2
13	88,9	87,9	90,1	95,7	96	91,7	8,1
14	88,1	89,2	90,4	96,4	99	92,6	10,9
15	86,7	91,7	92,1	90,9	95,1	91,3	8,4
16	86,9	88,6	91	91,9	95,9	90,9	9,0
17	88,7	89,4	93,1	92,1	98,6	92,4	9,9
18	87,6	87	94,3	95,3	94,5	91,7	8,3
19	85,7	90,3	92,5	96,2	97,2	92,4	11,5
20	90,0	88	89,9	90,3	95,2	90,7	7,2
						91,82	11,3

Using these measurements, firstly $\bar{X}$ the range of R values and the mean result of the range were calculated by formulas (1), (2), (3) and (4) $\bar{R}$ and $\bar{X}$ added to the graph column.

$\bar{X} = 91.82$ and $\bar{R} = 11.3$ the average values change as .

Using the measurement values and formulas (5), (6) and (7), the average updates of X control services are calculated and given below:

CURRENT SCIENCE

$$AKS = 91.82 - 0.577 * 11.3$$

$$AKS = 85.29$$

$$OÇ = 91.82$$

$$UKS = 91.82 + 0.577 * 11.3$$

$$UKS = 98.35$$

In addition, using formulas (8), (9) and (10), the R interval average update control services are calculated as follows:

$$AKS = 0 * 11.3$$

$$AKS = 0$$

$$OÇ = 11.3$$

$$UKS = 2.114 * 11.3$$

$$UKS = 23.92$$

According to these values obtained as a result of the calculations, X and R average diagrams are given in Figure 3 and Figure 4 below.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Figure 3: Initial X Mean Values

Figure 4: Initial R Range Mean Values

According to Figure 3, no breaches were found in the X average diagrams. However, in Figure 4's R break diagrams, the 5th and 10th subgroups included a break and the upper control limit started. This suggests that there was some slippage in the process.

This thrust subsystem alignment measurement test data set, the quantity detected in the 5th and 10th groups, should be re-evaluated, and the fighters required for analysis should be identified. Isolation of the topic should be avoided. There should be an explanation for this. This out-of-limit group must be removed and the scheme recreated.

According to what the firms conducted, the auxiliary thruster in the first area had a role in the rates of other tests. It was agreed to begin the rebuilding process immediately. It was discovered that the primary thruster engine in the fifth area of the other region was also damaged by the

CURRENT SCIENCE

collision owing to staff negligence. Work has begun on the required corrections. To avoid disturbances and to continue collecting data, the 5th and 10th samples were removed and the test continued. The next method will include planning without obtaining these two metrics, as well as the creation of a control chart.

Table 3 shows the angular measurement results for 18 units determined following these out-of-control readings.

Table 3: 18 Measurement Data Sets

Sample N	1. Region	2. Region	3. Region	4. Region	5. Region	X Average	R Range
1	85,0	87,1	93,8	95	96,2	91,4	11,2
2	85,6	87,5	94,9	90	96,9	91,0	11,3
3	85,9	88,3	89,1	90,1	94,8	89,6	8,9
4	86,2	89,5	95	96,9	95,7	92,7	10,7
5	85,9	91,9	89,7	94,1	98,7	92,1	12,8
6	89,0	91,1	93,7	93,2	98,1	93,0	9,1
7	88,5	89,9	92,8	95,9	97,5	92,9	9,0
8	87,4	88,8	94,1	97	94	92,3	9,6
9	86,6	90,8	91,3	92,8	97,9	91,9	11,3
10	87,1	91,3	89	96,7	98,3	92,5	11,2
11	88,9	87,9	90,1	95,7	96	91,7	8,1
12	88,1	89,2	90,4	96,4	99	92,6	10,9
13	86,7	91,7	92,1	90,9	95,1	91,3	8,4
14	86,9	88,6	91	91,9	95,9	90,9	9,0
15	88,7	89,4	93,1	92,1	98,6	92,4	9,9
16	87,6	87	94,3	95,3	94,5	91,7	8,3
17	85,7	90,3	92,5	96,2	97,2	92,4	11,5
18	90,0	88	89,9	90,3	95,2	90,7	7,2
						82,650	8,9

CURRENT SCIENCE

Using these measurements, X averages and R range values were calculated for the last time using the same formulas (1), (2), (3) and (4). They were added to the graphic column.

$\bar{X} = 82.65$ and $\bar{R} = 8.9$ the new average values as values.

Using the remaining measured values and formulas (5), (6) and (7) again, the average updates of the X control systems are calculated and given below:

$$AKS = 82.65 - 0.577 * 8.9$$

$$AKS = 77.50$$

$$OÇ = 82.65$$

$$UKS = 82.65 + 0.577 * 8.9$$

$$UKS = 87.80$$

For the new evaluation, using formulas (8), (9) and (10) once again, the average update control possibilities with R intervals are calculated as follows:

$$AKS = 0 * 8.9$$

$$AKS = 0$$

$$OÇ = 8.9$$

CURRENT SCIENCE

$$UKS = 2.114 * 8.9$$

$$UKS = 18.86$$

According to these values obtained as a result of the calculations, the X and R average diagrams are given in Figure 5 and Figure 6 below:

Figure 5: End X average values

Figure 6: Ending R Range Average Values

According to the updated values, no break or out-of-control condition was detected in the average X diagrams in Figure 5 or the R range diagrams in Figure 6. Standard deviations were not included in the control charts created to assist decision reversal, and evidence intervals were retained under process control.

To improve quality, the firm should analyze expansions with high error levels in angular measurement results and take steps to minimize them. Companies should utilize quality control charts that maximize benefits based on the margin of error in production growth and expansion.

CONCLUSION

It is possible to optimize the efficiency of satellite connections, cut expenses, and spend time more effectively by considering the sequence of control chart modes in test distributions. The application part includes Shewhart control charts that demonstrate the change in angular values acquired during the satellite alignment test phase using the preset settings. When the control charts were compared in two phases based on the study's averages, it was discovered that the process was out of control in the first measurements using the Shewhart control charts. The causes for this were studied, and after removing the data that disturbed the process, fresh Shewhart control charts were developed, bringing the process under control and recording the proper results.

It was determined that the average decision of process assessments and suitable control chart based simply on these did not fulfill the intended requirements. It was underlined that control charts for the variability of these scenarios should also be updated. According to Walter Shewhart, a well-known statistician, control limits placed three standard deviations in either direction from the mean vary depending on the shape of the process distribution, and a balance emerges between the risk of responding to false signals and the risk of cutting off the correct direction. There are many distribution types to utilize for the area under the curve based on the desired standard deviation amount.

As a consequence, evaluating the angular changes in the alignment test process using the Shewhart control chart allows for detailed monitoring of changing production processes. Furthermore, the viewpoint of the error control outcomes is significant. This operation will be able to identify deviations that may occur during the error control process early on, allowing for precautionary measures to be taken to prevent interruptions in the production process. This will make the product more economically viable, cut costs, and boost customer happiness.

RESOURCES

- Allen, T. T. (2006). An Introduction to Engineering Statistics and Six Sigma. *Springer London, England* , 29.
- Ertuğrul, İ. and Özçil, A. (2015). Application of “Shewart, Cusum and Ewma” from Quality Control Charts in a Manufacturing Enterprise, *KMÜ Journal of Social and Economic Research* , 17 (28), 14-26.
- ESA. (2015, 10 15). *Lisa Pathfinder* . <https://sci.esa.int/web/lisa-pathfinder/-/56737-alignment-tests-on-lisa-pathfinder>: Alignment tests performed on <https://sci.esa.int/web/lisa-pathfinder/-/56737-lisa-pathfinder>
- Noorossana, R. and Vaghefi, S. J. (2006). Effect of Autocorrelation on the Performance of M-Cusum Control Chart. *Quality and Reliability Engineering International* , 22(2), 191-197.
- Şahin, R. (2019). *Quality Engineering Lecture Notes* (pp. 140-152). In Ankara: Ahmet Yesevi University.
- Topalidou, E. and Psarakis, S. (2009). Investigation of Multi-Attribute and Multi-Attribute Quality Control Charts. *Quality and Reliability Engineering International* , 25(7), 773-804.
- Vries, A. D. and Conlin, J. (2005). Comparison of the Performance of Statistical Quality Control Charts in a Dairy Production System by Stochastic Simulation. *Agricultural Systems*, 84(3), 318-320.

CURRENT SCIENCE

About Authors

He works as a technician in a public sector expert institution. He is an Astronomer and Industrial Engineer. Rahmi Cenan completed his master's degree. He has a bachelor's degree in Business Administration. He is a student at St. Clements University. He is currently continuing his PhD in Business Administration.

rcenan@outlook.com and rcenan@turksat.com.tr .

Address: **TURKSAT** TURKSAT A.S.- Ankara- Turkey.